

SUBJECTIVE PERFORMANCE OF SELECTED SPEECH CODERS
IN THE PRESENCE OF CHANNEL ERRORS

Richard L. McKinley

United States Air Force
Aerospace Medical Research Laboratory
Wright-Patterson AFB, Ohio 45433

Richard V. Kurtz

TRW Defense Systems Group
1628 Springfield Street
Dayton, Ohio 45403

ABSTRACT

Speech intelligibility data of several voice coding techniques suitable for use in an air-to-air RF digital communication link is presented. The voice encoding techniques analyzed and their respective bit rates were as follows: adaptive differential pulse code modulation (ADPCM) at 24 kbps, continuously variable slope delta modulation (CVSD) at 16 kbps, sub-band coding (SBC) at 16 kbps, time domain harmonic scaling with sub-band coding (TDHS/SBC) at 9.6 kbps, and linear predictive coding (LPC-10) at 2.4 kbps. The RF digital communication link was simulated by random bit error insertion between the voice encoder and voice decoder. The resulting speech intelligibility performance was measured subjectively using the Modified Rhyme Test (MRT). Data graphs depicting speech intelligibility versus bit error rate (BER) are presented. This data shows that ADPCM and CVSD are most tolerant of bit errors, followed by SBC, TDHS/SBC, and LPC-10 in that order.

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this paper is to provide performance data on selected state-of-the-art voice coders under various bit error rate conditions and operated in realistic acoustic noise environments. This work was conducted in support of the Worldwide Airborne Command Post SPO at Tinker AFB, Oklahoma. In all, five different voice encoding techniques were analyzed: adaptive differential pulse code modulation (ADPCM), continuously variable slope delta modulation (CVSD), sub-band coding (SBC), time domain harmonic scaling with sub-band coding (TDHS/SBC), and linear predictive coding (LPC-10).

Due to time and economic considerations, each voice encoder was tested at only one bit rate. Two criteria were used in the selection of the bit rate. For the case where two or more voice encoders could be operated at the same bit rate, the voice encoder which was expected to perform best at that rate was selected. Otherwise, the voice encoder was operated at the lowest possible bit rate that gave "acceptable" performance. "Acceptable" performance was

defined as a Modified Rhyme Test (MRT) score of at least 80% under zero bit error rate conditions. One exception to the selection process was the CVSD coder, which was operated at 16 kbps so as to form a baseline for comparison with the results of previous experiments using CVSD at 16 kbps. The resulting voice encoders and bit rates addressed in this paper are as follows: ADPCM at 24 kbps, CVSD at 16 kbps, SBC at 16 kbps, TDHS/SBC at 9.6 kbps, and LPC at 2.4 kbps.

EQUIPMENT

The equipment configuration used for collection of the data presented in this paper was that of the Air Force Aerospace Medical Research Laboratory (AFAMRL) Voice Communication Research and Evaluation System (VOCRES) and is depicted in Figure 1 (ref. 1). The volunteer human listening panel were seated in an 8,000 cubic foot reverberation chamber with a high intensity sound system capable of reproducing wide band noise spectra from 20 Hz to 20 KHz at levels up to 125 dB. Each subject had an individual H-157 headset and standard AIC-25 aircraft intercommunication set. The encoder and decoder were the transmitting portion and receiving portion of the aforementioned voice coding techniques, respectively. Between the encoder and decoder, random bit errors were generated by special purpose hardware designed for this experiment. The wide range of voice coders investigated encompassed several different data transmission schemes, each of which was dealt with on an individual basis.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

This experiment used a crew of ten trained volunteer subjects who were paid an hourly wage for their participation in this experiment. All subjects had hearing threshold levels (HTL) better than 15 db at all audiometric frequencies from 125 Hz to 6,000 Hz. The experiments were carried out in the VOCRES facility using an airborne noise environment representative of a KC-135 during an orbit cruise at 28,000 feet. Spectral characterization of the EC-135 aircraft

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acoustic noise environment was not available. Of the available spectral characterizations, the KC-135 was selected as being most like the EC-135. The resulting KC-135 overall sound pressure level was 95 dB.

Each trial consisted of combinations of voice coder, bit error rate, and talker. Random trial combinations were selected to minimize the effects of ordering these areas. For each combination of voice coder and bit error rate, five different talkers were used, three male and two female. Each trial included listening scores from the other nine listeners. The listening scores were measured using the MRT, which is the test of choice for investigation of military voice communication systems (ref. 2).

The MRT is based on lists of 50 monosyllabic words of consonant-vowel-consonant construction. For each stimulus, six rhyming words are presented to the listener. These six words differ by only the initial or final consonant. Seventy-two different lists were used in this study. Each list has been shown to give equal intelligibility scores under controlled conditions. Because the MRT is a forced choice test, the data must be corrected for guessing. The adjustment is given by:

$$\text{Percent correct MRT adjusted for guessing} = 2.4 \times (\text{raw data point}) - 20.$$

Test sessions lasted approximately 45 minutes with a 15 minute rest break between each session. Four sessions were conducted each day which generated approximately 20 trials. Five coders, five bit error rates per coder, and five talkers for each combination of bit error rate and coder resulted in 125 total trials for the experiment.

DATA AND RESULTS

Speech intelligibility versus bit error rates for the coders investigated are shown in Figures 2 through 6. Figure 7 is a composite graph of all the data collected during the experiment. Each data point on the curves is a mean value of the 45 listening scores generated by the nine listeners and the five talkers. Past experience with military voice communication systems has shown that MRT scores greater than 80% are usually acceptable to operational users while MRT scores lower than 70% are usually unacceptable to the same group. The user acceptability of systems which score between 70% and 80% is uncertain.

The highest bit rate coder tested was ADPCM at 24 kbps, shown in Figure 2, which gave the highest overall intelligibility and exceptional

speech quality. The ADPCM algorithm was also remarkably tolerant of bit errors, with the 70% intelligibility point occurring with approximately 20% of the bits being in error.

CVSD at 16 kbps, shown in Figure 3, was found to have 7% less intelligibility at zero bit errors than ADPCM. The 70% intelligibility point came at a 17% bit error rate and fell off in much the same manner as did ADPCM. The overall quality of CVSD is lower due to the well known noisy sound resulting from quantization of the voice.

Shown in Figure 4, SBC at 16 kbps gave higher intelligibility with no bit errors than did CVSD at the same bit rate. The quality of the SBC coder was excellent for 16 kbps and was very near toll quality. SBC was, however, not as tolerant of bit errors as CVSD, with the 70% intelligibility point occurring at about a 10% bit error rate.

Referring to Figure 5, TDHS/SBC at 9.6 kbps gave the same initial intelligibility as CVSD at 16 kbps. In addition, the overall quality was better than that of CVSD. A slightly unnatural tone was heard, but was not offensive to the hearing of the listeners. TDHS/SBC intelligibility was greater than 70% for bit error rates less than about 1%.

LPC-10 at 2.4 kbps, shown in Figure 6, was the lowest bit rate coder investigated. Unfortunately, it also had the lowest zero bit rate intelligibility score. Like TDHS/SBC, LPC-10 is relatively susceptible to bit errors with the 70% intelligibility point coming at about the 1% bit error rate. Although LPC-10 does not degrade at higher bit error rates as rapidly as does TDHS/SBC, little difference occurs for the useful intelligibility region above 70%. LPC-10 has synthesized tonal components making the decoded audio quality machine-like.

SUMMARY

Five different voice coding algorithms were investigated at five different bit error rates using a human listening panel. The coders operated on speech that had been corrupted by ambient acoustical noise of 95 dB at the input microphone. For MRT intelligibility scores above 70% the results were as follows: ADPCM at 24 kbps tolerated 20% BER, CVSD at 16 kbps tolerated 17% BER, SBC at 16 kbps tolerated 10% BER, TDHS/SBC at 9.6 kbps tolerated 1% BER, and LPC-10 at 2.4 kbps tolerated 1% BER. Ranking the subjective voice quality with no bit errors from highest to lowest gives ADPCM at 24 kbps, SBC at 16 kbps, CVSD at 16 kbps, TDHS/SBC at 9.6 kbps, and LPC-10 at 2.4 kbps.

REFERENCES

- [1] Richard L. McKinley, Voice Communication Research and Evaluation System, AFAMRL-TR-80-25, Air Force Aerospace Medical Division, Air Force Systems Command, Wright-Patterson Air Force Base, May 1980.
- [2] J. C. Webster and C. R. Allen, Speech Intelligibility in Naval Aircraft Radios, NELC-TR-1830, August 1972.

Figure 1. Voice Equipment Configuration

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FIGURE 2. PERCENT INTELLIGIBILITY VERSUS BER FOR ADPCM 24 Kbps

FIGURE 3. PERCENT INTELLIGIBILITY VERSUS BER FOR CVSD 16 Kbps

FIGURE 4. PERCENT INTELLIGIBILITY VERSUS BER FOR SBC 16 Kbps

FIGURE 5. PERCENT INTELLIGIBILITY VERSUS BER FOR TDHS/SBC 9.6 Kbps

FIGURE 6. PERCENT INTELLIGIBILITY VERSUS BER FOR LPC 2.4 Kbps

FIGURE 7. COMPOSITE GRAPH OF INTELLIGIBILITY VERSUS BER FOR ALL FIVE VOICE ENCODERS